

Application of Preprocessing Techniques in Facial Recognition

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Abstract

Identifying and recognizing criminals at a crime scene can be a complex and time-consuming process. Criminals may be identified through various methods such as fingerprints, DNA analysis, CCTV footage, or eyewitness testimony. The use of images captured by security cameras, along with fingerprint and DNA matching, requires access to a pre-existing database for effective recognition. Similarly, systems designed for human identification, such as those used for access control or attendance tracking, also rely on image capture and a database for accurate identification.

This article discusses the methods for recognizing noised human faces by analyzing their features. Since images are multidimensional and can be affected by external factors that impact their clarity, creating an effective recognition model is a challenging task. To improve the system's accuracy, preprocessing techniques and feature extraction methods are applied to convert images into pixel-based data. The processed data is then fed into a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for classification and recognition. The study also examines the impact of three different preprocessing techniques and a comparative study of their effectiveness.

Keywords: Face recognition, Noise Reduction, Gaussian Filter, Amalgam Denoising Algorithm, Empirical Mode Decomposition; Intrinsic Mode Functions, Local Binary Pattern, Convolutional Neural Network.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recognizing criminals is a tedious process. In crime investigations, suspects can be identified using various methods. Facial recognition system paired with an existing criminal database to perform as an effective tool for criminal identification. In recent years, facial recognition has become a crucial component in criminal identification due to its ability to offer accurate and efficient identification. This research focuses on the method of identifying human faces through the use of distinctive features extracted from images. Developing a reliable computer model for face recognition is challenging due to the complexity and multidimensional nature of human faces.

The integration of facial recognition technology with surveillance systems can significantly enhance its effectiveness. By leveraging existing infrastructure like CCTV and body-worn cameras, law enforcement agencies can more efficiently identify and locate criminals. While many researchers have studied the integration of facial recognition systems into surveillance environments, they have also highlighted challenges related to compatibility and performance optimization. Despite this, previous studies have shown considerable variation in the accuracy of identification. Therefore, the primary aim of this research is to enhance the accuracy of criminal identification.

In addition to integration, this research also focuses on other critical processes such as image capture, preprocessing, feature extraction, matching, and refinement of facial characteristics.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Face recognition has become a critical focus in recent years due to its application in security, surveillance, and access control. The problem is complex due to the variation in facial features and expressions, as well as challenges in image capture, such as lighting conditions, facial expressions, and head poses. For instance, changes in lighting, facial expressions, and even obstructions like hats or glasses can affect recognition accuracy. Alireza Chevelwalla [1] addressed these challenges by storing facial images as segmented features in a database, paired with additional individual details. This paper reviews both model-based and appearance-based face recognition techniques, including PCA, LDA, and EBGGM algorithms.

Kaipeng Zhang [2] highlighted the difficulty of face detection in real-world settings, particularly when faces are obscured by objects like hats or facial expressions are hidden by reflections or shadows. Variations in facial structure, skin tone, and the presence of accessories such as glasses and masks further complicate face recognition tasks. To tackle these issues, Zhang employed deep learning techniques like convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and large datasets to identify patterns and features in faces, even under challenging conditions with noise and inconsistencies.

Nurul Azma Abdullah proposed an automated facial recognition system for criminal identification, which is an alternative to traditional thumb impressions [3]. Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), this system autonomously detects and identifies criminals' faces, even in the absence of fingerprints at crime scenes, with an accuracy of around 80% in matching images to the database.

For real-time criminal identification, Haar feature-based cascade classifiers have been utilized in automated face recognition systems [4]. The Viola-Jones approach, combined with OpenCV, ensures accurate detection of facial features in various situations.

In another study, Archana Naik [5] proposed a two-phase approach for facial recognition. In the first phase, the face is extracted from an image and its distinctive features are recorded in a database. In the second phase, comparisons are made between newly generated images and those stored in the database to retrieve the original information.

Piyush Chhoriya [6] designed a real-time face identification system using a security camera, supported by Python and the OpenCV library. The system operates in four stages: image

training, face detection using Haar cascades, comparison of trained images with captured images, and displaying the results.

Aakriti Singhal [7] developed a method that stores both full and segmented images of criminals, along with other details. Eyewitnesses can help reconstruct the face using these segmented images, and the reconstructed face is compared to the database using AWS Identification. If a match rate of 70-80% is found, the criminal is identified.

Deep learning techniques, particularly CNNs, have been widely adopted for face identification, achieving notable accuracy rates. In one study, CNNs were used to develop a face identification system with a large dataset, yielding 91.7% accuracy in image recognition and 86.7% accuracy in real-time video recognition [9]. Factors like insufficient lighting and the training duration of the model can influence accuracy [10].

Nagnath B. Aherwadi and colleagues [11] employed CCTV cameras in public settings to capture criminal images. After extracting features from these images, they were stored and compared against a database, yielding more than 80% match accuracy.

Saniya Prashant Patil et al. [12] introduced a real-time surveillance system using deep learning to detect both exposed and partially covered faces (such as those wearing masks or hijabs).

A novel deep convolutional network was proposed in [13], where the authors used triplets of aligned face patches for training, resulting in an accuracy of 99.63% on the Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) dataset and 95.12% on the YouTube Face database. This approach significantly reduced the error rate by 30% compared to previous models. In a recent project [15], machine learning techniques were used for criminal identification, focusing on CCTV footage from surveillance cameras. The system aims to identify suspects and criminals when fingerprint or other biological evidence is unavailable.

CNNs, combined with Haar Cascade classifiers, have been applied for criminal face detection and recognition in [16]. CNNs help in object detection and facial feature identification, while Haar cascades improve face detection accuracy. This system, trained on dynamic datasets, can identify criminals and send location alerts to authorities.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques were further integrated in [17], using the Amalgam denoising algorithm for image cleansing and the Binary Gradient Alignment (BGA) method for criminal classification, achieved an accuracy of 97.35%. This system also includes an alarm feature, which alerts officials when a match is found in public surveillance areas. These developments in face recognition systems demonstrate the increasing integration of advanced technologies in security applications, enhancing their ability to identify criminals in real-time and under diverse conditions.

3. DENOISING TECHNIQUES

The most crucial step in image or data processing across various systems is noise reduction, often referred to as smoothing, preprocessing, or filtering. During image capture, different types of noise can occur due to fluctuations in light intensity, which may impact the camera sensor and result in inaccurate pixel values. These imperfections can lead to the storage of

faulty or dark pixels, lowering the overall quality of the image. Additionally, issues such as sensor defects, errors during image capture, or external factors like climate changes can introduce noise during the conversion of an analog signal into digital form. Other problems, such as rounding errors or inaccuracies in signal representation, can further degrade image clarity, affecting subsequent analysis. Therefore, applying noise reduction techniques is essential to improve image quality and ensure more accurate analysis.

Various preprocessing methods are employed to reduce noise in images, including median filtering, Gaussian filtering, anisotropic diffusion, wavelet-based denoising, dark frame correction, flat fielding, Wiener filtering, curvelet transform, image averaging and spatial averaging. Additionally, advanced techniques involving artificial intelligence and deep learning, such as adversarial generative networks and convolutional neural networks, are increasingly used for noise removal and to effectively identify patterns [18-22]. In this study, we are reviewing the performance of Curvelet transformation, Empirical Mode Decomposition and Amalgam Denoising Algorithm.

3.1 Curvelet Tranform

The curvelet transform is a multiscale, directional tool used in image processing to capture image features at various scales and orientations. It extends the wavelet transform, addressing some of the shortcomings of wavelets and Gabor filters [23]. By decomposing an image into a series of subbands or scales, the curvelet transform is particularly effective at representing the edges and curves in an image. This theory can be applied to a novel edge detection method. The key concept is that the values of curvelet coefficients are influenced by their alignment with edges in the image: the closer the alignment, the higher the coefficient value [24]. By analyzing these coefficients, it becomes knowledgeable that each scale level contains distinct types of information. Therefore, by sorting the coefficients at each scale and emphasizing the most significant ones, edge-related features of the image are enhanced. These enhanced coefficients are then reconstructed into a new image, highlighting the edges. Finally, morphological filters are used to remove noise and improve the quality of the resulting image.

3.1.1. Subband Decomposition

The image is initially broken down into wavelet sub-bands based on its size. Then, Curvelet sub-bands are generated by partially reconstructing these wavelet sub-bands at different levels.

The original image divided into different resolution layers with different frequencies.

$$I = (L_f I, H_{f_1} I, H_{f_2} I, H_{f_3} I, \dots \dots \dots, H_{f_n} I)$$

$$L_f = \text{Lowpass filter}$$

$$H_f = \text{Highpass filters}$$

The original can be reformed from sub-bands by using,

$$I = (L_f(L_f I) + \sum_{s=0}^{s=n} L_{f_s}(L_{f_s} I)$$

3.1.2. Smooth Partitioning

In this stage, each subband is smoothly segmented into squares at a suitable scale.

A collection of smooth window is defined as,

$$S_w(x_1, y_1)$$

S= smooth window function with support size $2^{-s} \times 2^{-s}$.

Multiplying a function by the corresponding window function S_w produces a result localized near W ($\forall W \in W_s$).

Repeating it for all W at a certain scale is $W = W_{(s,a_1,b_1)}$ where, a_1 and b_1 are varying, s is fixed.

Smooth window is localized around the dyadic squares,

$$W_{(s,a_1,b_1)} = \left[\frac{a_1}{2^s}, \frac{a_1 + 1}{2^s} \right] \times \left[\frac{b_1}{2^s}, \frac{b_1 + 1}{2^s} \right] \in W_s$$

Apply the window dissection to each subbands and it produces a smooth dissection of squares.

$$t_w = S_w \times H_{fs}$$

The image become smooth after multiplying S_w .

The partitioning is easier to analyze curve singularities.

3.1.3. Renormalization

Here, the resulting squares are renormalized into unit scale.

For a dyadic square,

$$D_w I(x_1, y_1) = 2^s I(2^s x_1 - a_1, 2^s y_1 - b_1)$$

It transports and renormalizes I .

Each square is renormalized to unit scale,

$$R_{nw} = D_w^{-1} t_w$$

3.1.4. Ridgelet Transform

In last two stages, curved lines break down into smaller straight segments. This enhances the Curvelet transform's ability to effectively capture curved edges. The Ridgelet Transform is particularly effective for handling line singularities in two dimensions. The main concept involves using the Radon transform to map a line singularity in a 2D space to a point. Once this transformation is applied, a one-dimensional wavelet is used to address the point singularity in the Radon domain [25].

The ridgelet construction divides the frequency domain to dyadic corona $|\xi| \in [2^s, 2^{s+1}]$.

The ridgelet element has a formula in the frequency domain and each normalized square is analyzed,

$$\alpha_{(w,\lambda)} = \|R_{nw}, \rho_\lambda\|$$

A ridge fragment representation needs only few ridgelet coefficients.

3.1.5. Inverse Curvelet Transform

a) Ridgelet Synthesis

All squares are reconstructed with orthonormal ridgelet.

Summation all the Ridgelet coefficients are,

$$R_{nw} = \sum_{\lambda} \alpha_{(w,\lambda)} \times \rho_\lambda$$

b) Renormalization / Merge the blocks

Resulting squares are renormalized to its proper squares,

$$t_w = D_w R_{nw}$$

$$W \in W_s$$

c) Smooth Integration

Reverse the window dissection to each windows recreated in previous stage.

$$H_{fs}I = \sum_{w \in W_s} S_w \times t_w$$

d) Subband Recomposition

Reproducing formula is used for the summation all the subbands,

$$I = L_f(L_f I) + \sum_s H_{fs}(H_{fs}I)$$

3.2 Empirical Mode Decomposition

The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) is a method that adaptively breaks down a complex signal into Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs), which reflect the intrinsic physical characteristics of the signal. Each IMF is symmetric, and it is important to note that achieving both a local frequency and a constant frequency at a single time point across different IMFs is not feasible [26]. IMFs can be applied to both linear and nonlinear pixel data derived from images. This technique is signal-dependent, requiring no specific assumptions about stability or linearity. Each IMF corresponds to a single oscillation mode, which is typically characterized by zero crossings. As a result, complex waves in an image are not suitable for this method [31].

The process of extracting IMFs, often referred to as the "sifting process," involves working with an image $im(T)$. The first step is to identify the local maxima and minima to generate upper and lower envelopes using interpolation techniques such as linear, piecewise spline, or cubic spline. Next, the local mean, denoted as $m(T)$, is computed by averaging the upper and lower envelopes. Finally, $m(T)$ is subtracted from the original signal T to obtain the desired IMFs.

$$X_i(T) = im(T) - m_i(T)$$

If $X_i(T)$ is found as an IMF, the process stop there and mark first IMF as $x_1(T)$.

Else, $im(T)$ is replaced with $X_i(T)$ and reiterate the whole process by identifying local minima and maxima.

Apply the process of sifting to the residue $x_2(T) = im(T) - x_1(T)$, for the 2nd IMF.

Likewise, the 3rd IMF is determined by $x_3(T) = x_2(T) - x_1(T)$ and so on.

When 2 consecutive sifting become identical or close to it, the process stops IMF and generation of EMD is,

$$im(T) = \sum_1^n x_1 + x_n$$

Where, $x_n = \text{constant residue}$

$n = n \text{ empirical mode decomposition}$

If 1st mode is having highest frequency, the processed image generates $pim(T)$ with 1st 50% of modes,

$$pim(T) = \sum_1^{\frac{n}{2}} x_i$$

Fig.1: Input image

Fig.2: Generated IMF functions of the figure 1, with respect to the time

Binarization is applied to the resulting image, where pixels are assigned one of two distinct values. The homogeneous face region is represented in white, while the remaining areas are shown in black. After binarization, edge detection is performed to identify the boundaries within the image.

Fig.3: Binarization of IMF functions with respect to the time

Fig. 4(a): Six IMFs and the residue decomposed from face images of female

Fig. 4(b): Six IMFs and the residue decomposed from face images of male

3.3 Amalgam Denoising Algorithm

The Amalgam Denoising Algorithm (ADA) [28] offers the advantage of combining the strengths of four distinct evolutionary optimization algorithms: Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Adaptive Metropolis Search (AMS) and Differential Evolution (DE) [28-31]. The approach employs a self-adaptive offspring generation mechanism and a concurrent multi-method search strategy [32].

Initially, the Amalgam algorithm generates a random initial population X , of a specified size using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). Each sample, X_i is then assigned a rank based on fast non-domination sorting. A proposal population X_x , of the same size is generated through a multimethod search to identify promising algorithms within Amalgam. To do this, the genetic algorithm is applied to the sample X_i producing a set of individuals,

$N = \{N_i^1, N_i^2, \dots, N_i^n\}$. The best N solutions, selected from the combined population $C_i = X_i \cup \bar{X}_i$, are incorporated into the next generation X_{i+1} , using the fast non-domination sorting operator. This search process, along with the adaptive offspring generation, continues iterating until the stopping criterion or a predefined number of iterations is reached. The integration of PSO, DE, and AMS ensures a diverse approach to generating offspring in each iteration, with their individual offspring counts being dynamically managed.

$$\{N_i^1, N_i^2, \dots, N_i^n\}$$

$$\text{Where, } N_i^n = N \times \frac{\left\{ \left\{ \frac{L_i^a}{N_{i-1}^a} \right\} \right\}}{\left\{ \left[\frac{\sum_1^a L_i^n}{N_{i-1}^n} \right] \right\}}$$

Where,

L_i^n = matching count (in last generation)

$$\left\{ \frac{L_i^a}{N_{i-1}^a} \right\} = \text{new population (proportion)}$$

Fig.4:(a) Noise image (Original) and Denoised Image of female

Fig.4:(a) Noise image (Original) and Denoised Image of male

4. DISCUSSION

The Curvelet Transform is a multiscale and multidirectional representation that extends wavelet competences to capture curved features in images more accurately. Unlike wavelets, it perform well for point singularities. Curvelet Transform performs by applying a transform to the noisy image, thresholding the coefficients, and then reconstructing the denoised image. This method effectively reduces Gaussian and speckle noise while preserving important structural features such as edges and contours.

EMD is a data-driven technique that decomposes a signal into a series of intrinsic mode functions (IMFs). Each IMF represents oscillatory modes. EMD is more suited for analyzing nonlinear and non-stationary time-series data such as speech, ECG, and vibration, where frequency and amplitude change over time. Denoising is achieved by discarding or thresholding IMFs associated with noise, then reconstructing the signal.

Amalgam Denoising Algorithms are hybrid techniques that integrate multiple denoising methods, such as Curvelet Transform, EMD, and wavelet thresholding. This algorithm aim to combine the best attributes of each method for improved noise suppression. Therefore, ADA achieves better peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), structural similarity (SSIM), and visual quality than single-method approaches and so, it is used for complex denoising from mixed noise types or multifaceted data. Table 1 shows the comparative study of these three techniques in terms of its advantages, disadvantages, edge preservation of the method, efficiency in removing noise types, most suitable for the type of images, computational complexity, suitable application of the methods for denoising and the typical output quality.

Table 1: The identified strength and weakness of the algorithms

Sr. No.	Denoising Technique	CT	EMD	ADA
1	Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Superior edge and texture preservation • Effective in reducing high-frequency noise • Suitable for 2D and 3D image processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully adaptive, no need for a predefined basis • Good for time-localized frequency analysis • Suitable for real-world 1D signals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust against various noise types • Balanced performance in edge preservation and signal clarity • Customizable to specific domains
2	Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High computational load • Threshold selection impacts performance • Less adaptive to signal variations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mode mixing (overlap of frequencies in IMFs) • Not inherently designed for multidimensional data • Sensitive to noise and endpoint effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High computational complexity • Implementation challenges due to parameter tuning • Not ideal for real-time systems without optimization
3	Edge Preservation	Very good	Moderate	Excellent
4	Noise Type	Gaussian, colored noise	Non-Gaussian, impulsive noise	Mixed/no complex noise
5	Most suitability	Image denoising with strong edges	1D signal denoising, nonstationary signals	Complex scenarios needing robust denoising
6	Computational Complexity	High	Moderate	Very high
7	Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical image denoising. • Seismic data processing. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image compression. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speech and audio denoising. • Biomedical signal processing (ECG, EEG). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanical vibration analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex signals/images where noise has multiple characteristics. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situations demanding high-fidelity recovery, e.g., advanced medical imaging, seismic data analysis.
8	Output Quality	Sharp edges, less blurring	Smooth components, risk of	Balanced quality, better edge

			mode mixing	preservation
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5. CONCLUSION

The denoising algorithms are developed to mitigate the distractions of the images and so improve the accuracy in classification or segmentation process. Each denoising method has unique advantages and limitations. The Curvelet Transform is ideal for image denoising where preserving geometric features is crucial. While CT is preserving the edges of the image, EMD excels in adaptive decomposition of nonlinear and non-stationary signals. Amalgam Denoising Algorithms is a hybrid method and it combine the strengths of multiple methodologies for accurate and robust noise suppression. ADA is computationally expensive but, provide enhanced performance by fusing complementary techniques. In this research, ADA performs well when compared to other two techniques. The selection of appropriate denoising technique and its accuracy always depends on the type of data, noise characteristics, and available computational resources.

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